

**Citation for the Presentation of the 2020
ICPE Medal to**

**Professor Alex Mazzolini
Australia**

**at Australian Academy of Science Meeting
Australia
10th December 2020**

Professor Alex Mazzolini's Citation and Medal Ceremony.

Prof. Mazzolini's Medal Ceremony was hosted in the Australian Institute of Physics and Australian Academy of Science Meeting on 10th December 2020, in Australia. Prof. Alex Mazzolini was presented (virtually) with the ICPE medal for his "outstanding contributions to physics teaching of a kind that transcends national boundaries". The medal is awarded in recognition of contributions to physics education that have extended over a considerable number of years and are international in their scope and influence.

Alex Mazzolini has been working in physics education for more than 40 years. In that time, he has mentored and inspired countless students and educators in the training and workshops he has delivered across 6 continents and more than 40 countries. One of his important contributions has been through the UNESCO Active Learning in Optics and Photonics (ALOP) program, which he co-founded in 2003. During the meeting, Alex shared highlights from his learning and teaching journey.

Prof. Manjula Sharma, member of ICPE and colleagues from AIP chaired the session and shared memories about Prof. Mazzolini's academic life and his dedication to the physics teaching in Australia and other countries. Prof. Roberto Nardi, chair of the C14 Commission and other members participated in the ceremony. Alex gave an inspiring talk. Mazzolini, a copy of the medal and online participants are illustrated in the photos/screenshots below.

